

declined sharply 1 month after the deep-water rice harvest. Crop losses caused by rice root-knot nematode were studied in pots and in the field. Populations of 2,000 nematodes/plant caused severe stunting of root and shoot development in pots and reduced yield more than 60%. Field populations of 1,000 nematodes/kg soil caused poor plant growth and yields.

Carbofuran 3 kg ai/ha incorporated at sowing significantly reduced infestation, but did not significantly increase yields at Rajbari, Joydebpur.

Forty-one entries were screened in a preliminary pot test. Although no entries

Yield and ufra disease incidence of deepwater rice under different planting and nematicide treatments.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Ufra disease (incidence %)
Broadcast seed	0.24	77.2
Broadcast seed with carbofuran	0.44	58.3
Transplanted	0.59	52.9
Transplanted with carbofuran	0.94	36.7

resisted infection, 5 had low infection, as judged by gall counts and microscopic examination of root tissues.

White tip disease caused by Aphelenchoides besseyi Christie, 1942. Deepwater rice areas were widely surveyed for white tip disease symptoms. Only one new area of infestation — Dubail, Tangail — was recorded.

The Gazaria beel at Manikganj, where the disease was a problem in 1981 was comprehensively surveyed. More than 56% of the fields were infested. In most, 5 to 10% of the rice stems showed disease symptoms. Disease incidence at flowering stage of Rajboalia was not reflected in the number of infected panicles at harvest. Nevertheless, the disease affected all yield components. □

Soil and crop management

Efficiency of different urea fertilizers in lowland rice

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Applied fertilizer nitrogen (N) efficiency in lowland rice is low. We evaluated the effect of water regime and urea fertilizers on rice dry matter yield and N uptake in the greenhouse using a completely randomized design in three replications. The soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrepts) with pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.23% organic carbon, 0.04% total N, and 4.54 meq CEC/100 g. The N levels were 0 and 115 mg/kg. The urea materials were 3 splits of prilled urea (PUS), urea in mudball (MBU), urea supergranules (USG), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), neem cake-coated urea (NCU), and lac-coated urea (LCU). A no-nitrogen check also was planted. The water regimes consisted of continuous soil submergence with and without drainage. Drainage was maintained at a percolation rate of 5 mm/h by using pinch corks at drainage outlets.

Soil samples of 8 kg each at the 15-cm depth were air-dried, ground, and treated with 26 mg P/kg and 50 mg K/kg applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash respectively. The soil was placed in 10-liter pots, flooded, pud-

Effect of drainage and urea materials on dry matter yields and N uptake of rice plants.^a

Urea material	Without drainage		With drainage	
	Dry matter (g/pot)	N uptake (mg/pot)	Dry matter (g/pot)	N uptake (mg/pot)
Check	9.8 a	118 a	17.2 a	262 a
Prilled urea 3 splits	37.2 c	850 cd	36.3 c	625 b
Urea in mudball	36.4 c	897 d	32.8 bc	603 b
Urea supergranule	40.3 c	910 d	21.2 a	366 a
Sulfur-coated urea	29.3 b	691 b	32.9 bc	695 b
Neem cake-coated urea	28.5 b	721 bc	29.5 b	650 b
Lac-coated urea	29.5 b	705 b	29.6 b	577 b
Interaction ^b	DU**	DU**	DU**	DU**

^aCV for dry matter = 9.9%; CV for N uptake = 12.7%. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b**P = 0.01, D = drainage treatment, U = urea material.

dled, and where appropriate, treated with 115 mg N/kg. Urea materials, except PUS, were either deep-placed 5-7 cm or broadcast and incorporated 5-7 cm deep. Four 27-day-old PR106 seedlings were planted in each pot. The pots were flooded to maintain 5 cm of standing water and, where appropriate, drainage was imposed. Plants were harvested 60 d after transplanting and dry matter yields were recorded. N uptake was computed using dry matter data and Kjeldahl N in the rice plants.

Without drainage, dry matter yields and N uptake were significantly depressed

Cumulative leaching losses of total N (urea + NH₄⁺ -N) from a lowland rice soil.

in the check, NCU, SCU, and LCU compared to MBU, PUS, and USG (see table).

With drainage, dry matter yield and N uptake with SCU equaled that with PUS and MBU. LCU and NCU also showed a similar trend. Dry matter yield and N uptake were significantly depressed

with USG, and equaled the dry matter yield and N uptake of the check. Dry matter yield and N uptake of the check were twice what they were with no drainage.

With drainage, the low dry matter yield and N uptake with USG was caused

by cumulative leaching losses of total N (urea + NH_4^+ -N) (see figure). Nitrogen leaching losses were 62.1% for USG, 19.1% for NCU, 16.9% for LCU, 14.3% for PUS, and 13.0% for MBU. No leaching losses of urea or NH_4^+ -N were recorded for SCU.

Effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure on yield and micronutrient content of rice

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A field experiment to determine the effect of micronutrients and farmyard manure (FYM) was conducted on a sodic soil with sand + silt 85.4%, clay 14.6%, CaCO_3 2.45%, pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage 92, CEC 10.0 meq/100 g, gypsum requirement 25 t/ha; and DTPA extractable Fe, Mn, and Zn 3.5, 4.2, and 0.45 ppm, respectively, at Gudha experimental farm of CSSRI.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with 4 replications of 5 micronutrient treatments: T1, control, no micronutrient; T2, 20 ppm Fe; T3, 20 ppm Mn; T4, 5 ppm Zn; and T5, 20 ppm Fe + 20 ppm Mn + 5 ppm Zn and 0 and 10 t FYM/ha. FYM contained 0.85% N, 0.35% P, 0.78% K, 0.35% Ca, 0.24% Mg, 0.22% S, 52 ppm Zn, 125 ppm Mn, 10 ppm Cu, and 320 ppm Fe. Fifty percent of the gypsum requirement was broadcast and mixed and all plots received 150 kg N/ha as urea. Micronutrient sources were $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Plot size was 40m². Micronutrients, FYM, and 75 kg N/ha were broadcast and disced into the soil. Plots

Effect of micronutrients and FYM on rice yield and micronutrient concentration.

Treatment	FYM rate (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha)		Micronutrient concn (ppm)						
		Grain	Straw	Zn			Fe		Mn	
				Leaves	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Control	0	5.0	8.0	8.5	8.1	10.5	45	335	40	285
	10	5.3	8.3	9.6	9.9	12.8	55	375	48	340
Fe (20 ppm)	0	5.0	8.0	8.4	8.0	10.4	52	360	46	295
	10	5.4	8.4	9.8	10.0	13.1	68	415	52	365
Mn (20 ppm)	0	5.2	8.2	8.6	8.5	10.6	46	340	51	315
	10	5.6	8.7	11.2	11.8	18.2	55	380	58	425
Zn (5 ppm)	0	5.6	8.7	15.5	12.9	25.4	45	340	42	280
	10	6.0	9.1	20.6	15.8	30.5	56	380	48	345
Fe+Mn+Zn	0	6.0	9.1	15.4	12.8	26.8	50	365	55	325
	10	6.0	9.3	21.8	15.1	31.8	68	425	62	480
CD (0.05) for comparing										
FYM level means		0.22	0.35	1.2	0.9	0.7	8	20	6	18
Micronutrient means		0.33	0.44	1.0	0.8	1.6	5	14	3	10

were irrigated and 30-day-old Jaya rice seedlings were transplanted 15 Jul 1979. The remaining 75 kg N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 weeks of crop growth. Leaf samples of 30-day-old plants (3d and 4th leaves from the top) were collected and plant samples were taken at harvest 1 Nov 1979.

Zn application significantly enhanced the grain and straw yield (see table). Fe and Mn did not affect yield but the highest yield was recorded when these elements were applied with Zn.

Crop growth was poor in plots without Zn and symptoms of moderate

Zn deficiency were noticed at early growth stage (25-30 days). FYM significantly enhanced the yield, irrespective of the micronutrient treatment, possibly because of the increased availability of Zn caused by its application. Zn concentration in 30-day-old leaves was less than the critical 10 ppm value in plots where it was not applied because available soil Zn was less than the critical 0.55 ppm level. Application of Fe, Mn, and Zn enhanced their respective concentration in the crop. FYM also effectively increased micronutrient concentration in the crop.

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned rice and normal sown aman rice

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Ratooned and normal sown aman rice varieties were compared. Photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties SR26B, FR13A, Tillakkachari and Achra 108/1 were sown on 14 Nov 1981 and harvested May 1982. Ratooned tillers grew in the fields. A sim-

Comparison of photoperiod-sensitive ratooned and normal sown aman rice, Chinsurah, India, 1981-82.

Variety	Aman sown rice				Ratooned rice			
	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
SR26B	146	22	7	3.7	158	24	11	2.5
FR13A	113	22	8	3.8	146	25	11	3.0
Tillakkachari	142	24	9	3.8	170	26	13	5.0
Achra 108/1	132	25	7	3.9	170	27	11	4.8
Mean	133	23	8	3.7	161	26	12	3.8